

Form **990**

Return of Organization Exempt From Income Tax

OMB No. 1545-0047

2016

Under section 501(c), 527, or 4947(a)(1) of the Internal Revenue Code (except private foundations)

Do not enter social security numbers on this form as it may be made public.

Information about Form 990 and its instructions is at www.irs.gov/form990.

Open to Public Inspection

Department of the Treasury
Internal Revenue Service

A For the 2016 calendar year, or tax year beginning _____, and ending _____

B Check if applicable:
 Address change
 Name change
 Initial return
 Final return/terminated
 Amended return
 Application pending

C Name of organization: **FACES & VOICES OF RECOVERY**
 Doing business as _____
 Number and street (or P.O. box if mail is not delivered to street address) Room/suite
840 1ST STREET 3RD FLOOR
 City or town State ZIP code
WASHINGTON DC 20002
 Foreign country name Foreign province/state/county Foreign postal code

D Employer identification number: **51-0516206**

E Telephone number: **(202) 737-0690**

G Gross receipts \$: **471,941**

F Name and address of principal officer: **PATTY MCCARTHY-METCALF 840 1st Street 3rd Floor, Washington, DC**
 H(a) Is this a group return for subordinates? Yes No
 H(b) Are all subordinates included? Yes No
 If "No," attach a list. (see instructions)

I Tax-exempt status: 501(c)(3) 501(c) () (insert no.) 4947(a)(1) or 527

J Website: **WWW.FACESANDVOICESOFRECOVERY.ORG**
 H(c) Group exemption number _____

K Form of organization: Corporation Trust Association Other _____
 L Year of formation: **2004** M State of legal domicile: **DC**

Part I Summary		Prior Year	Current Year
Activities & Governance	1 Briefly describe the organization's mission or most significant activities: <u>To broaden the social understanding of and increase support for the people seeking long term recovery from alcohol & other drug addiction, their families, friends and allies; To change the public perception of recovery.</u>		
	2 Check this box ☐ if the organization discontinued its operations or disposed of more than 25% of its net assets.		
	3 Number of voting members of the governing body (Part VI, line 1a)	3	11
	4 Number of independent voting members of the governing body (Part VI, line 1b)	4	11
	5 Total number of individuals employed in calendar year 2016 (Part V, line 2a)	5	8
	6 Total number of volunteers (estimate if necessary)	6	
	7a Total unrelated business revenue from Part VIII, column (C), line 12	7a	0
b Net unrelated business taxable income from Form 990-T, line 34	7b	0	
Revenue	8 Contributions and grants (Part VIII, line 1h)	187,809	189,841
	9 Program service revenue (Part VIII, line 2g)	210,874	277,567
	10 Investment income (Part VIII, column (A), lines 3, 4, and 7d)	0	0
	11 Other revenue (Part VIII, column (A), lines 5, 6d, 8c, 9c, 10c, and 11e)	385	4,533
	12 Total revenue—add lines 8 through 11 (must equal Part VIII, column (A), line 12)	399,068	471,941
Expenses	13 Grants and similar amounts paid (Part IX, column (A), lines 1–3)	0	0
	14 Benefits paid to or for members (Part IX, column (A), line 4)	0	0
	15 Salaries, other compensation, employee benefits (Part IX, column (A), lines 5–10)	174,616	220,532
	16a Professional fundraising fees (Part IX, column (A), line 11e)	0	0
	b Total fundraising expenses (Part IX, column (D), line 25) 49,607		
17 Other expenses (Part IX, column (A), lines 11a–11d, 11f–24e)	228,477	264,473	
18 Total expenses. Add lines 13–17 (must equal Part IX, column (A), line 25)	403,093	485,005	
19 Revenue less expenses (Subtract line 18 from line 12)	-4,025	-13,064	
Net Assets or Fund Balances	20 Total assets (Part X, line 16)	Beginning of Current Year 127,059	End of Year 50,143
	21 Total liabilities (Part X, line 26)	136,074	72,222
	22 Net assets or fund balances (Subtract line 21 from line 20)	-9,015	-22,079

Part II Signature Block

Under penalties of perjury, I declare that I have examined this return, including accompanying schedules and statements, and to the best of my knowledge and belief, it is true, correct, and complete. Declaration of preparer (other than officer) is based on all information of which preparer has any knowledge.

Sign Here
 Signature of officer: Patty McCarthy Metcalf Date: 11-15-17
 Name and title: **PATTY MCCARTHY METCALF EXECUTIVE DIRECTOR**

Paid Preparer Use Only
 Print/preparer's name: **SCOTT N DRAPER, CPA MBA** Preparer's signature: Scott N Draper Date: 11/15/2017 Check self-employed or PTIN: **P00608551**
 Firm's name: **N.Y.T. CERTIFIED PUBLIC ACCOUNTANTS LLC** Firm's EIN: **52-2272961**
 Firm's address: **864 JEFFERSON BLVD, HAGERSTOWN, MD 21740** Phone no.: **301-797-6609**

May the IRS discuss this return with the preparer shown above? (see instructions) Yes No

SCANNED DEC 11 2017

560
16.071

Part III Statement of Program Service Accomplishments

Check if Schedule O contains a response or note to any line in this Part III []

1 Briefly describe the organization's mission: TO ORGANIZE & MOBILIZE THE MILLIONS OF AMERICANS IN LONG TERM RECOVERY FROM ALCOHOL AND OTHER DRUG ADDICTION, THEIR FAMILIES, FRIENDS AND ALLIES TO SPEAK WITH ONE VOICE, CHANGE PUBLIC PERCEPTION OF RECOVERY, PROMOTING EFFECTIVE PUBLIC POLICY AND DEMONSTRATING SUCCESS IN RECOVERY

2 Did the organization undertake any significant program services during the year which were not listed on the prior Form 990 or 990-EZ? [] Yes [X] No If "Yes," describe these new services on Schedule O

3 Did the organization cease conducting, or make significant changes in how it conducts, any program services? [] Yes [X] No If "Yes," describe these changes on Schedule O

4 Describe the organization's program service accomplishments for each of its three largest program services, as measured by expenses Section 501(c)(3) and 501(c)(4) organizations are required to report the amount of grants and allocations to others, the total expenses, and revenue, if any, for each program service reported

4a (Code) (Expenses \$ 304,904 including grants of \$) (Revenue \$) FACES & VOICES OF RECOVERY SUPPORTS ALL PATHWAYS TO RECOVERY FROM ADDICTION TO ALCOHOL AND OTHER DRUGS BY CONDUCTING PUBLIC EDUCATION AND AWARENESS CAMPAIGNS AND RESEARCH INTO RECOVERY FACES & VOICES HOSTS EDUCATIONAL AND INFORMATIONAL TRAININGS AND OTHER ACTIVITES, FACILITATING RELATIONSHIPS AMONG LOCAL AND REGIONAL RECOVERY ORGANIZATIONS AND PROVIDES A NATIONAL FORUM FOR DISCUSSION FACES & VOICES CREATED THE FIRST EVER "RECOVERY BILL OF RIGHTS", A DECLARATION STATING THAT ALL AMERICANS HAVE A RIGHT TO BE FREE FROM ADDICTION AND TO BUILD NEW LIVES AND ORGANIZES WALKS AND RALLIES AS PART OF NATIONAL ALCOHOL AND DRUG ADDICTION RECOVERY MONTH FACES & VOICES OF RECOVERY PRODUCES A BI-MONTHLY E-NEWSLETTER AND TRAINING DVDS ON THE SCIENCE OF ADDICTION AND RECOVERY AND OTHER TOPICS THEY HAVE DEVELOPED AND MAINTAIN A MULTI-FACETED ONE-STEP RECOVERY WEB-SITE WITH INFORMATION FOR CITIZENS, FAMILIES AND THOSE IN LONG TERM RECOVERY ON HOW TO GET INVOLVED IN THEIR COMMUNITIES

4b (Code) (Expenses \$ including grants of \$) (Revenue \$)

4c (Code) (Expenses \$ including grants of \$) (Revenue \$)

4d Other program services (Describe in Schedule O) (Expenses \$ 0 including grants of \$ 0) (Revenue \$ 0)

4e Total program service expenses 304,904

Part IV Checklist of Required Schedules

	Yes	No
1 Is the organization described in section 501(c)(3) or 4947(a)(1) (other than a private foundation)? If "Yes," complete Schedule A	X	
2 Is the organization required to complete Schedule B, Schedule of Contributors (see instructions)?	X	
3 Did the organization engage in direct or indirect political campaign activities on behalf of or in opposition to candidates for public office? If "Yes," complete Schedule C, Part I		X
4 Section 501(c)(3) organizations. Did the organization engage in lobbying activities, or have a section 501(h) election in effect during the tax year? If "Yes," complete Schedule C, Part II		X
5 Is the organization a section 501(c)(4), 501(c)(5), or 501(c)(6) organization that receives membership dues, assessments, or similar amounts as defined in Revenue Procedure 98-19? If "Yes," complete Schedule C, Part III		X
6 Did the organization maintain any donor advised funds or any similar funds or accounts for which donors have the right to provide advice on the distribution or investment of amounts in such funds or accounts? If "Yes," complete Schedule D, Part I		X
7 Did the organization receive or hold a conservation easement, including easements to preserve open space, the environment, historic land areas, or historic structures? If "Yes," complete Schedule D, Part II		X
8 Did the organization maintain collections of works of art, historical treasures, or other similar assets? If "Yes," complete Schedule D, Part III		X
9 Did the organization report an amount in Part X, line 21, for escrow or custodial account liability, serve as a custodian for amounts not listed in Part X, or provide credit counseling, debt management, credit repair, or debt negotiation services? If "Yes," complete Schedule D, Part IV		X
10 Did the organization, directly or through a related organization, hold assets in temporarily restricted endowments, permanent endowments, or quasi-endowments? If "Yes," complete Schedule D, Part V		X
11 If the organization's answer to any of the following questions is "Yes," then complete Schedule D, Parts VI, VII, VIII, IX, or X as applicable		
a Did the organization report an amount for land, buildings, and equipment in Part X, line 10? If "Yes," complete Schedule D, Part VI	X	
b Did the organization report an amount for investments—other securities in Part X, line 12 that is 5% or more of its total assets reported in Part X, line 16? If "Yes," complete Schedule D, Part VII		X
c Did the organization report an amount for investments—program related in Part X, line 13 that is 5% or more of its total assets reported in Part X, line 16? If "Yes," complete Schedule D, Part VIII		X
d Did the organization report an amount for other assets in Part X, line 15 that is 5% or more of its total assets reported in Part X, line 16? If "Yes," complete Schedule D, Part IX	X	
e Did the organization report an amount for other liabilities in Part X, line 25? If "Yes," complete Schedule D, Part X	X	
f Did the organization's separate or consolidated financial statements for the tax year include a footnote that addresses the organization's liability for uncertain tax positions under FIN 48 (ASC 740)? If "Yes," complete Schedule D, Part X	X	
12a Did the organization obtain separate, independent audited financial statements for the tax year? If "Yes," complete Schedule D, Parts XI and XII	X	
b Was the organization included in consolidated, independent audited financial statements for the tax year? If "Yes," and if the organization answered "No" to line 12a, then completing Schedule D, Parts XI and XII is optional		X
13 Is the organization a school described in section 170(b)(1)(A)(ii)? If "Yes," complete Schedule E		X
14a Did the organization maintain an office, employees, or agents outside of the United States?		X
b Did the organization have aggregate revenues or expenses of more than \$10,000 from grantmaking, fundraising, business, investment, and program service activities outside the United States, or aggregate foreign investments valued at \$100,000 or more? If "Yes," complete Schedule F, Parts I and IV		X
15 Did the organization report on Part IX, column (A), line 3, more than \$5,000 of grants or other assistance to or for any foreign organization? If "Yes," complete Schedule F, Parts II and IV		X
16 Did the organization report on Part IX, column (A), line 3, more than \$5,000 of aggregate grants or other assistance to or for foreign individuals? If "Yes," complete Schedule F, Parts III and IV		X
17 Did the organization report a total of more than \$15,000 of expenses for professional fundraising services on Part IX, column (A), lines 6 and 11e? If "Yes," complete Schedule G, Part I (see instructions)		X
18 Did the organization report more than \$15,000 total of fundraising event gross income and contributions on Part VIII, lines 1c and 8a? If "Yes," complete Schedule G, Part II	X	
19 Did the organization report more than \$15,000 of gross income from gaming activities on Part VIII, line 9a? If "Yes," complete Schedule G, Part III		X

Part IV Checklist of Required Schedules (continued)

	Yes	No
20a Did the organization operate one or more hospital facilities? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule H</i>		X
b If "Yes" to line 20a, did the organization attach a copy of its audited financial statements to this return?		
21 Did the organization report more than \$5,000 of grants or other assistance to any domestic organization or domestic government on Part IX, column (A), line 1? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule I, Parts I and II</i>		X
22 Did the organization report more than \$5,000 of grants or other assistance to or for domestic individuals on Part IX, column (A), line 2? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule I, Parts I and III</i>		X
23 Did the organization answer "Yes" to Part VII, Section A, line 3, 4, or 5 about compensation of the organization's current and former officers, directors, trustees, key employees, and highest compensated employees? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule J</i>		X
24a Did the organization have a tax-exempt bond issue with an outstanding principal amount of more than \$100,000 as of the last day of the year, that was issued after December 31, 2002? <i>If "Yes," answer lines 24b through 24d and complete Schedule K. If "No," go to line 25a</i>		X
b Did the organization invest any proceeds of tax-exempt bonds beyond a temporary period exception?		X
c Did the organization maintain an escrow account other than a refunding escrow at any time during the year to defease any tax-exempt bonds?		X
d Did the organization act as an "on behalf of" issuer for bonds outstanding at any time during the year?		X
25a Section 501(c)(3), 501(c)(4), and 501(c)(29) organizations. Did the organization engage in an excess benefit transaction with a disqualified person during the year? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule L, Part I</i>		X
b Is the organization aware that it engaged in an excess benefit transaction with a disqualified person in a prior year, and that the transaction has not been reported on any of the organization's prior Forms 990 or 990-EZ? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule L, Part I</i>		X
26 Did the organization report any amount on Part X, line 5, 6, or 22 for receivables from or payables to any current or former officers, directors, trustees, key employees, highest compensated employees, or disqualified persons? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule L, Part II</i>		X
27 Did the organization provide a grant or other assistance to an officer, director, trustee, key employee, substantial contributor or employee thereof, a grant selection committee member, or to a 35% controlled entity or family member of any of these persons? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule L, Part III</i>		X
28 Was the organization a party to a business transaction with one of the following parties (see Schedule L, Part IV instructions for applicable filing thresholds, conditions, and exceptions)		
a A current or former officer, director, trustee, or key employee? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule L, Part IV</i>		X
b A family member of a current or former officer, director, trustee, or key employee? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule L, Part IV</i>		X
c An entity of which a current or former officer, director, trustee, or key employee (or a family member thereof) was an officer, director, trustee, or direct or indirect owner? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule L, Part IV</i>		X
29 Did the organization receive more than \$25,000 in non-cash contributions? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule M</i>		X
30 Did the organization receive contributions of art, historical treasures, or other similar assets, or qualified conservation contributions? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule M</i>		X
31 Did the organization liquidate, terminate, or dissolve and cease operations? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule N, Part I</i>		X
32 Did the organization sell, exchange, dispose of, or transfer more than 25% of its net assets? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule N, Part II</i>		X
33 Did the organization own 100% of an entity disregarded as separate from the organization under Regulations sections 301.7701-2 and 301.7701-3? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule R, Part I</i>		X
34 Was the organization related to any tax-exempt or taxable entity? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule R, Part II, III, or IV, and Part V, line 1</i>		X
35a Did the organization have a controlled entity within the meaning of section 512(b)(13)?		
b If "Yes" to line 35a, did the organization receive any payment from or engage in any transaction with a controlled entity within the meaning of section 512(b)(13)? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule R, Part V, line 2</i>		
36 Section 501(c)(3) organizations. Did the organization make any transfers to an exempt non-charitable related organization? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule R, Part V, line 2</i>		X
37 Did the organization conduct more than 5% of its activities through an entity that is not a related organization and that is treated as a partnership for federal income tax purposes? <i>If "Yes," complete Schedule R, Part VI</i>		X
38 Did the organization complete Schedule O and provide explanations in Schedule O for Part VI, lines 11b and 19? Note. All Form 990 filers are required to complete Schedule O	X	

Part V Statements Regarding Other IRS Filings and Tax Compliance

Check if Schedule O contains a response or note to any line in this Part V

Table with columns for line numbers (1a-14b), descriptions of questions, and Yes/No checkboxes. Includes sections for backup withholding, employee reporting, foreign accounts, prohibited transactions, and charitable contributions.

Part VI Governance, Management, and Disclosure For each "Yes" response to lines 2 through 7b below, and for a "No" response to line 8a, 8b, or 10b below, describe the circumstances, processes, or changes in Schedule O. See instructions. Check if Schedule O contains a response or note to any line in this Part VI.

Section A. Governing Body and Management

		Yes	No
1a	Enter the number of voting members of the governing body at the end of the tax year. If there are material differences in voting rights among members of the governing body, or if the governing body delegated broad authority to an executive committee or similar committee, explain in Schedule O.		
1b	Enter the number of voting members included in line 1a, above, who are independent.		
2	Did any officer, director, trustee, or key employee have a family relationship or a business relationship with any other officer, director, trustee, or key employee?		X
3	Did the organization delegate control over management duties customarily performed by or under the direct supervision of officers, directors, or trustees, or key employees to a management company or other person?		X
4	Did the organization make any significant changes to its governing documents since the prior Form 990 was filed?		X
5	Did the organization become aware during the year of a significant diversion of the organization's assets?		X
6	Did the organization have members or stockholders?		X
7a	Did the organization have members, stockholders, or other persons who had the power to elect or appoint one or more members of the governing body?		X
7b	Are any governance decisions of the organization reserved to (or subject to approval by) members, stockholders, or persons other than the governing body?		X
8	Did the organization contemporaneously document the meetings held or written actions undertaken during the year by the following:		
8a	The governing body?	X	
8b	Each committee with authority to act on behalf of the governing body?	X	
9	Is there any officer, director, trustee, or key employee listed in Part VII, Section A, who cannot be reached at the organization's mailing address? If "Yes," provide the names and addresses in Schedule O.		X

Section B. Policies (This Section B requests information about policies not required by the Internal Revenue Code.)

		Yes	No
10a	Did the organization have local chapters, branches, or affiliates?		X
10b	If "Yes," did the organization have written policies and procedures governing the activities of such chapters, affiliates, and branches to ensure their operations are consistent with the organization's exempt purposes?		
11a	Has the organization provided a complete copy of this Form 990 to all members of its governing body before filing the form?	X	
11b	Describe in Schedule O the process, if any, used by the organization to review this Form 990.		
12a	Did the organization have a written conflict of interest policy? If "No," go to line 13.	X	
12b	Were officers, directors, or trustees, and key employees required to disclose annually interests that could give rise to conflicts?	X	
12c	Did the organization regularly and consistently monitor and enforce compliance with the policy? If "Yes," describe in Schedule O how this was done.	X	
13	Did the organization have a written whistleblower policy?	X	
14	Did the organization have a written document retention and destruction policy?	X	
15	Did the process for determining compensation of the following persons include a review and approval by independent persons, comparability data, and contemporaneous substantiation of the deliberation and decision?		
15a	The organization's CEO, Executive Director, or top management official	X	
15b	Other officers or key employees of the organization. If "Yes" to line 15a or 15b, describe the process in Schedule O (see instructions).		X
16a	Did the organization invest in, contribute assets to, or participate in a joint venture or similar arrangement with a taxable entity during the year?		X
16b	If "Yes," did the organization follow a written policy or procedure requiring the organization to evaluate its participation in joint venture arrangements under applicable federal tax law, and take steps to safeguard the organization's exempt status with respect to such arrangements?		

Section C. Disclosure

17 List the states with which a copy of this Form 990 is required to be filed ▶ NONE

18 Section 6104 requires an organization to make its Forms 1023 (or 1024 if applicable), 990, and 990-T (Section 501(c)(3)s only) available for public inspection. Indicate how you made these available. Check all that apply.
 Own website Another's website Upon request Other (explain in Schedule O)

19 Describe in Schedule O whether (and if so, how) the organization made its governing documents, conflict of interest policy, and financial statements available to the public during the tax year.

20 State the name, address, and telephone number of the person who possesses the organization's books and records: ▶
 THE ORGANIZATION (202) 737-0690
 840 1ST ST NE 3RD FLOOR, WASHINGTON, DC 20002

Part VII Compensation of Officers, Directors, Trustees, Key Employees, Highest Compensated Employees, and Independent Contractors

Check if Schedule O contains a response or note to any line in this Part VII

Section A. Officers, Directors, Trustees, Key Employees, and Highest Compensated Employees

1a Complete this table for all persons required to be listed Report compensation for the calendar year ending with or within the organization's tax year

- List all of the organization's **current** officers, directors, trustees (whether individuals or organizations), regardless of amount of compensation Enter -0- in columns (D), (E), and (F) if no compensation was paid
- List all of the organization's **current** key employees, if any See instructions for definition of "key employee "
- List the organization's five **current** highest compensated employees (other than an officer, director, trustee, or key employee) who received reportable compensation (Box 5 of Form W-2 and/or Box 7 of Form 1099-MISC) of more than \$100,000 from the organization and any related organizations
 - List all of the organization's **former** officers, key employees, and highest compensated employees who received more than \$100,000 of reportable compensation from the organization and any related organizations
 - List all of the organization's **former directors or trustees** that received, in the capacity as a former director or trustee of the organization, more than \$10,000 of reportable compensation from the organization and any related organizations

List persons in the following order individual trustees or directors, institutional trustees, officers, key employees, highest compensated employees, and former such persons

Check this box if neither the organization nor any related organization compensated any current officer, director, or trustee

(A) Name and Title	(B) Average hours per week (list any hours for related organizations below dotted line)	(C) Position (do not check more than one box, unless person is both an officer and a director/trustee)						(D) Reportable compensation from the organization (W-2/1099-MISC)	(E) Reportable compensation from related organizations (W-2/1099-MISC)	(F) Estimated amount of other compensation from the organization and related organizations
		Individual trustee or director	Institutional trustee	Officer	Key employee	Highest compensated employee	Former			
(1) JAN BROWN DIRECTOR-AT-LARGE	2 00 0 00	X								
(2) GLORIA NEPOTE DIRECTOR-MID AMERICA	2 00 0 00	X								
(3) MARYANNE FRANGULES SECRETARY	2 00 0 00	X		X						
(4) H WESTLEY CLARK DIRECTOR - AT-LARGE	2 00 0 00	X								
(5) SIS WENGER DIRECTOR-AT-LARGE	2 00 0 00	X								
(6) TIM CHENEY TREASURER	4 00 0 00	X		X						
(7) RICHARD BUCKMAN CHAIR	4 00 0 00	X		X						
(8) BEVERLY HABERLE VICE CHAIR	2 00 0 00	X		X						
(9) TOM PATTON DIRECTOR-AT-LARGE	2 00 0 00	X								
(10) MARY BONO DIRECTOR-AT-LARGE	2 00 0 00	X								
(11) NEIL CAMPBELL DIRECTOR-AT-LARGE	2 00 0 00	X								
(12) PATTY MCCARTHY METCALF EXEC DIRECTOR	40 00 0 00				X		103,846			
(13)										
(14)										

Part VII Section A. Officers, Directors, Trustees, Key Employees, and Highest Compensated Employees (continued)

(A) Name and title	(B) Average hours per week (list any hours for related organizations below dotted line)	(C) Position (do not check more than one box, unless person is both an officer and a director/trustee)						(D) Reportable compensation from the organization (W-2/1099-MISC)	(E) Reportable compensation from related organizations (W-2/1099-MISC)	(F) Estimated amount of other compensation from the organization and related organizations
		Individual trustee or director	Institutional trustee	Officer	Key employee	Highest compensated employee	Former			
(15)										
(16)										
(17)										
(18)										
(19)										
(20)										
(21)										
(22)										
(23)										
(24)										
(25)										
1b Sub-total							103,846	0	0	
c Total from continuation sheets to Part VII, Section A							0	0	0	
d Total (add lines 1b and 1c)							103,846	0	0	

2 Total number of individuals (including but not limited to those listed above) who received more than \$100,000 of reportable compensation from the organization **1**

3 Did the organization list any **former** officer, director, or trustee, key employee, or highest compensated employee on line 1a? *If "Yes," complete Schedule J for such individual*

	Yes	No
3		X
4		X
5		X

4 For any individual listed on line 1a, is the sum of reportable compensation and other compensation from the organization and related organizations greater than \$150,000? *If "Yes," complete Schedule J for such individual*

5 Did any person listed on line 1a receive or accrue compensation from any unrelated organization or individual for services rendered to the organization? *If "Yes," complete Schedule J for such person*

Section B. Independent Contractors

1 Complete this table for your five highest compensated independent contractors that received more than \$100,000 of compensation from the organization Report compensation for the calendar year ending with or within the organization's tax year

(A) Name and business address	(B) Description of services	(C) Compensation
		0
		0
		0
		0
		0

2 Total number of independent contractors (including but not limited to those listed above) who received more than \$100,000 of compensation from the organization **0**

Part VIII Statement of Revenue

Check if Schedule O contains a response or note to any line in this Part VIII

		(A) Total revenue	(B) Related or exempt function revenue	(C) Unrelated business revenue	(D) Revenue excluded from tax under sections 512-514	
Contributions, Gifts, Grants and Other Similar Amounts	1a Federated campaigns	1a 0				
	b Membership dues	1b 47,134				
	c Fundraising events	1c 0				
	d Related organizations	1d 0				
	e Government grants (contributions)	1e 0				
	f All other contributions, gifts, grants, and similar amounts not included above	1f 142,707				
	g Noncash contributions included in lines 1a-1f.	\$ 0				
	h Total. Add lines 1a-1f	▶ 189,841				
Program Service Revenue	Business Code					
	2a CONTRACTS	541610	220,668			
	b CONSULTING & HONORARIA	541610	8,310			
	c TRAINING-REGISTRATION	541610	13,950			
	d MERCHANDISE	541610	5,711			
	e ACCREDITATION FEES	541610	28,928			
	f All other program service revenue		0			
	g Total. Add lines 2a-2f	▶ 277,567				
Other Revenue	3 Investment income (including dividends, interest, and other similar amounts)	▶ 0				
	4 Income from investment of tax-exempt bond proceeds	▶ 0				
	5 Royalties	▶ 0				
	6a Gross rents	(i) Real				
		(ii) Personal				
	b Less rental expenses					
	c Rental income or (loss)	0	0			
	d Net rental income or (loss)	▶ 0				
	7a Gross amount from sales of assets other than inventory	(i) Securities				
		(ii) Other				
			0	0		
	b Less cost or other basis and sales expenses	0	0			
	c Gain or (loss)	0	0			
d Net gain or (loss)	▶ 0					
8a Gross income from fundraising events (not including \$ 127,300 of contributions reported on line 1c) See Part IV, line 18	a	0				
	b Less direct expenses	0				
	c Net income or (loss) from fundraising events	▶ 0				
9a Gross income from gaming activities See Part IV, line 19	a	0				
	b Less direct expenses	0				
	c Net income or (loss) from gaming activities	▶ 0				
10a Gross sales of inventory, less returns and allowances	a	0				
	b Less cost of goods sold	0				
	c Net income or (loss) from sales of inventory	▶ 0				
Miscellaneous Revenue		Business Code				
11a OTHER REVENUE		4,533				
b		0				
c		0				
d All other revenue		0				
e Total. Add lines 11a-11d	▶ 4,533					
12 Total revenue. See instructions	▶ 471,941		0	0	0	

Part IX Statement of Functional Expenses

Section 501(c)(3) and 501(c)(4) organizations must complete all columns. All other organizations must complete column (A)

Check if Schedule O contains a response or note to any line in this Part IX

Do not include amounts reported on lines 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b, and 10b of Part VIII.	(A) Total expenses	(B) Program service expenses	(C) Management and general expenses	(D) Fundraising expenses
1 Grants and other assistance to domestic organizations domestic governments See Part IV, line 21	0			
2 Grants and other assistance to domestic individuals See Part IV, line 22	0			
3 Grants and other assistance to foreign organizations, foreign governments, and foreign individuals See Part IV, lines 15 and 16	0			
4 Benefits paid to or for members	0			
5 Compensation of current officers, directors, trustees, and key employees	0		0	
6 Compensation not included above, to disqualified persons (as defined under section 4958(f)(1)) and persons described in section 4958(c)(3)(B)	0			
7 Other salaries and wages	190,464	127,611	41,902	20,951
8 Pension plan accruals and contributions (include section 401(k) and 403(b) employer contributions)	0			
9 Other employee benefits	12,427	8,326	2,734	1,367
10 Payroll taxes	17,641	11,819	3,881	1,941
11 Fees for services (non-employees)				
a Management	0			
b Legal	0			
c Accounting	17,171		17,171	
d Lobbying	0			
e Professional fundraising services See Part IV, line 17	0			
f Investment management fees	0			
g Other (If line 11g amount exceeds 10% of line 25, column (A) amount, list line 11g expenses on Schedule O)	7,249		7,249	
12 Advertising and promotion	6,819	3,410		3,409
13 Office expenses	16,679	3,434	9,811	3,434
14 Information technology	2,220	1,554	555	111
15 Royalties	0			
16 Occupancy	33,910	20,346	11,868	1,696
17 Travel	43,062	21,960	21,102	
18 Payments of travel or entertainment expenses for any federal, state, or local public officials	0			
19 Conferences, conventions, and meetings	0			
20 Interest	1,460		1,460	
21 Payments to affiliates	0			
22 Depreciation, depletion, and amortization	12,745	11,827	918	0
23 Insurance	11,958	5,979	5,979	
24 Other expenses Itemize expenses not covered above (List miscellaneous expenses in line 24e. If line 24e amount exceeds 10% of line 25, column (A) amount, list line 24e expenses on Schedule O)				
a SPECIAL EVENTS	57,491	43,945		13,546
b CONSULTANTS	37,128	37,128		
c TELEPHONE	5,549	3,607	1,387	555
d PRINTING	3,508	176	2,280	1,052
e All other expenses	7,524	3,782	2,197	1,545
25 Total functional expenses. Add lines 1 through 24e	485,005	304,904	130,494	49,607
26 Joint costs. Complete this line only if the organization reported in column (B) joint costs from a combined educational campaign and fundraising solicitation. Check here ☐ if following SOP 98-2 (ASC 958-720)				

Part X Balance Sheet

Check if Schedule O contains a response or note to any line in this Part X

		(A) Beginning of year		(B) End of year
Assets	1 Cash—non-interest-bearing	34,270	1	36,194
	2 Savings and temporary cash investments		2	
	3 Pledges and grants receivable, net	0	3	0
	4 Accounts receivable, net	64,375	4	1,755
	5 Loans and other receivables from current and former officers, directors, trustees, key employees, and highest compensated employees Complete Part II of Schedule L		5	
	6 Loans and other receivables from other disqualified persons (as defined under section 4958(f)(1)), persons described in section 4958(c)(3)(B), and contributing employers and sponsoring organizations of section 501(c)(9) voluntary employees' beneficiary organizations (see instructions) Complete Part II of Schedule L		6	
	7 Notes and loans receivable, net	0	7	0
	8 Inventories for sale or use		8	
	9 Prepaid expenses and deferred charges	8,681	9	1,492
	10a Land, buildings, and equipment cost or other basis Complete Part VI of Schedule D	10a 80,267		
	b Less accumulated depreciation	10b 73,201	15,894	10c 7,066
	11 Investments—publicly traded securities	0	11	0
	12 Investments—other securities See Part IV, line 11	0	12	0
	13 Investments—program-related See Part IV, line 11	0	13	0
	14 Intangible assets	0	14	0
	15 Other assets See Part IV, line 11	3,839	15	3,636
16 Total assets. Add lines 1 through 15 (must equal line 34)	127,059	16	50,143	
Liabilities	17 Accounts payable and accrued expenses	19,370	17	15,199
	18 Grants payable		18	
	19 Deferred revenue	42,516	19	0
	20 Tax-exempt bond liabilities		20	
	21 Escrow or custodial account liability Complete Part IV of Schedule D		21	
	22 Loans and other payables to current and former officers, directors, trustees, key employees, highest compensated employees, and disqualified persons Complete Part II of Schedule L		22	
	23 Secured mortgages and notes payable to unrelated third parties	0	23	0
	24 Unsecured notes and loans payable to unrelated third parties	27,275	24	20,303
	25 Other liabilities (including federal income tax, payables to related third parties, and other liabilities not included on lines 17-24) Complete Part X of Schedule D	46,913	25	36,720
	26 Total liabilities. Add lines 17 through 25	136,074	26	72,222
Net Assets or Fund Balances	Organizations that follow SFAS 117 (ASC 958), check here ☒ and complete lines 27 through 29, and lines 33 and 34.			
	27 Unrestricted net assets	-9,015	27	-22,079
	28 Temporarily restricted net assets		28	
	29 Permanently restricted net assets		29	
	Organizations that do not follow SFAS 117 (ASC958), check here ☐ and complete lines 30 through 34.			
	30 Capital stock or trust principal, or current funds		30	
	31 Paid-in or capital surplus, or land, building, or equipment fund		31	
	32 Retained earnings, endowment, accumulated income, or other funds		32	
33 Total net assets or fund balances	-9,015	33	-22,079	
34 Total liabilities and net assets/fund balances	127,059	34	50,143	

Part XI Reconciliation of Net Assets

Check if Schedule O contains a response or note to any line in this Part XI

1	Total revenue (must equal Part VIII, column (A), line 12)	1	471,941
2	Total expenses (must equal Part IX, column (A), line 25)	2	485,005
3	Revenue less expenses Subtract line 2 from line 1	3	-13,064
4	Net assets or fund balances at beginning of year (must equal Part X, line 33, column (A))	4	-9,015
5	Net unrealized gains (losses) on investments	5	
6	Donated services and use of facilities	6	
7	Investment expenses	7	
8	Prior period adjustments	8	
9	Other changes in net assets or fund balances (explain in Schedule O)	9	
10	Net assets or fund balances at end of year Combine lines 3 through 9 (must equal Part X, line 33, column (B))	10	-22,079

Part XII Financial Statements and Reporting

Check if Schedule O contains a response or note to any line in this Part XII

		Yes	No
1	Accounting method used to prepare the Form 990 ☐ Cash ☒ Accrual ☐ Other If the organization changed its method of accounting from a prior year or checked "Other," explain in Schedule O		
2a	Were the organization's financial statements compiled or reviewed by an independent accountant? If "Yes," check a box below to indicate whether the financial statements for the year were compiled or reviewed on a separate basis, consolidated basis, or both ☐ Separate basis ☐ Consolidated basis ☐ Both consolidated and separate basis		X
b	Were the organization's financial statements audited by an independent accountant? If "Yes," check a box below to indicate whether the financial statements for the year were audited on a separate basis, consolidated basis, or both ☐ Separate basis ☒ Consolidated basis ☐ Both consolidated and separate basis	X	
c	If "Yes" to line 2a or 2b, does the organization have a committee that assumes responsibility for oversight of the audit, review, or compilation of its financial statements and selection of an independent accountant? If the organization changed either its oversight process or selection process during the tax year, explain in Schedule O	X	
3a	As a result of a federal award, was the organization required to undergo an audit or audits as set forth in the Single Audit Act and OMB Circular A-133?		X
b	If "Yes," did the organization undergo the required audit or audits? If the organization did not undergo the required audit or audits, explain why in Schedule O and describe any steps taken to undergo such audits		

SCHEDULE A
(Form 990 or 990-EZ)

Public Charity Status and Public Support

OMB No 1545-0047

2016

Open to Public Inspection

Complete if the organization is a section 501(c)(3) organization or a section 4947(a)(1) nonexempt charitable trust.

▶ **Attach to Form 990 or Form 990-EZ.**

▶ **Information about Schedule A (Form 990 or 990-EZ) and its instructions is at www.irs.gov/form990.**

Department of the Treasury
Internal Revenue Service

Name of the organization

FACES & VOICES OF RECOVERY

Employer identification number

51-0516206

Part I Reason for Public Charity Status (All organizations must complete this part) See instructions.

The organization is not a private foundation because it is (For lines 1 through 12, check only one box)

- 1 A church, convention of churches, or association of churches described in **section 170(b)(1)(A)(i)**.
- 2 A school described in **section 170(b)(1)(A)(ii)**. (Attach Schedule E (Form 990 or 990-EZ))
- 3 A hospital or a cooperative hospital service organization described in **section 170(b)(1)(A)(iii)**.
- 4 A medical research organization operated in conjunction with a hospital described in **section 170(b)(1)(A)(iii)**. Enter the hospital's name, city, and state _____
- 5 An organization operated for the benefit of a college or university owned or operated by a governmental unit described in **section 170(b)(1)(A)(iv)**. (Complete Part II)
- 6 A federal, state, or local government or governmental unit described in **section 170(b)(1)(A)(v)**.
- 7 An organization that normally receives a substantial part of its support from a governmental unit or from the general public described in **section 170(b)(1)(A)(vi)**. (Complete Part II)
- 8 A community trust described in **section 170(b)(1)(A)(vi)**. (Complete Part II)
- 9 An agricultural research organization described in **section 170(b)(1)(A)(ix)** operated in conjunction with a land-grant college or university or a non-land-grant college of agriculture (see instructions) Enter the name, city, and state of the college or university: _____
- 10 An organization that normally receives (1) more than 33 1/3% of its support from contributions, membership fees, and gross receipts from activities related to its exempt functions—subject to certain exceptions, and (2) no more than 33 1/3% of its support from gross investment income and unrelated business taxable income (less section 511 tax) from businesses acquired by the organization after June 30, 1975 See **section 509(a)(2)**. (Complete Part III)
- 11 An organization organized and operated exclusively to test for public safety See **section 509(a)(4)**.
- 12 An organization organized and operated exclusively for the benefit of, to perform the functions of, or to carry out the purposes of one or more publicly supported organizations described in **section 509(a)(1)** or **section 509(a)(2)**. See **section 509(a)(3)**. Check the box in lines 12a through 12d that describes the type of supporting organization and complete lines 12e, 12f, and 12g
 - a **Type I.** A supporting organization operated, supervised, or controlled by its supported organization(s), typically by giving the supported organization(s) the power to regularly appoint or elect a majority of the directors or trustees of the supporting organization **You must complete Part IV, Sections A and B.**
 - b **Type II.** A supporting organization supervised or controlled in connection with its supported organization(s), by having control or management of the supporting organization vested in the same persons that control or manage the supported organization(s) **You must complete Part IV, Sections A and C.**
 - c **Type III functionally integrated.** A supporting organization operated in connection with, and functionally integrated with, its supported organization(s) (see instructions) **You must complete Part IV, Sections A, D, and E.**
 - d **Type III non-functionally integrated.** A supporting organization operated in connection with its supported organization(s) that is not functionally integrated The organization generally must satisfy a distribution requirement and an attentiveness requirement (see instructions) **You must complete Part IV, Sections A and D, and Part V.**
 - e Check this box if the organization received a written determination from the IRS that it is a Type I, Type II, Type III functionally integrated, or Type III non-functionally integrated supporting organization
 - f Enter the number of supported organizations 0
 - g Provide the following information about the supported organization(s)

(i) Name of supported organization	(ii) EIN	(iii) Type of organization (described on lines 1–10 above (see instructions))	(iv) Is the organization listed in your governing document?		(v) Amount of monetary support (see instructions)	(vi) Amount of other support (see instructions)
			Yes	No		
(A)						
(B)						
(C)						
(D)						
(E)						
Total					0	0

Part II Support Schedule for Organizations Described in Sections 170(b)(1)(A)(iv) and 170(b)(1)(A)(vi)

(Complete only if you checked the box on line 5, 7, or 8 of Part I or if the organization failed to qualify under Part III. If the organization fails to qualify under the tests listed below, please complete Part III.)

Section A. Public Support

Calendar year (or fiscal year beginning in)	(a) 2012	(b) 2013	(c) 2014	(d) 2015	(e) 2016	(f) Total
1 Gifts, grants, contributions, and membership fees received (Do not include any "unusual grants")	186,841	480,442	236,535	187,809	189,841	1,281,468
2 Tax revenues levied for the organization's benefit and either paid to or expended on its behalf						0
3 The value of services or facilities furnished by a governmental unit to the organization without charge						0
4 Total. Add lines 1 through 3	186,841	480,442	236,535	187,809	189,841	1,281,468
5 The portion of total contributions by each person (other than a governmental unit or publicly supported organization) included on line 1 that exceeds 2% of the amount shown on line 11, column (f)						
6 Public support. Subtract line 5 from line 4						1,281,468

Section B. Total Support

Calendar year (or fiscal year beginning in)	(a) 2012	(b) 2013	(c) 2014	(d) 2015	(e) 2016	(f) Total
7 Amounts from line 4	186,841	480,442	236,535	187,809	189,841	1,281,468
8 Gross income from interest, dividends, payments received on securities loans, rents, royalties and income from similar sources						0
9 Net income from unrelated business activities, whether or not the business is regularly carried on						0
10 Other income. Do not include gain or loss from the sale of capital assets (Explain in Part VI)	2,791	226	5,557	385	4,533	13,492
11 Total support. Add lines 7 through 10						1,294,960

12 Gross receipts from related activities, etc (see instructions) **12**

13 First five years. If the Form 990 is for the organization's first, second, third, fourth, or fifth tax year as a section 501(c)(3) organization, check this box and stop here

Section C. Computation of Public Support Percentage

14 Public support percentage for 2016 (line 6, column (f) divided by line 11, column (f))	14	98.96%
15 Public support percentage from 2015 Schedule A, Part II, line 14	15	99.44%

16a 33 1/3% support test—2016. If the organization did not check the box on line 13, and line 14 is 33 1/3% or more, and stop here. The organization qualifies as a publicly supported organization

b 33 1/3% support test—2015. If the organization did not check a box on line 13 or 16a, and line 15 is 33 1/3% or more, check this box and stop here. The organization qualifies as a publicly supported organization

17a 10%-facts-and-circumstances test—2016. If the organization did not check a box on line 13, 16a, or 16b, and line 14 is 10% or more, and if the organization meets the "facts-and-circumstances" test, check this box and stop here. Explain in Part VI how the organization meets the "facts-and-circumstances" test The organization qualifies as a publicly supported organization

b 10%-facts-and-circumstances test—2015. If the organization did not check a box on line 13, 16a, 16b, or 17a, and line 15 is 10% or more, and if the organization meets the "facts-and-circumstances" test, check this box and stop here. Explain in Part VI how the organization meets the "facts-and-circumstances" test The organization qualifies as a publicly supported organization

18 Private foundation. If the organization did not check a box on line 13, 16a, 16b, 17a, or 17b, check this box and see instructions

Part III Support Schedule for Organizations Described in Section 509(a)(2)

(Complete only if you checked the box on line 10 of Part I or if the organization failed to qualify under Part II. If the organization fails to qualify under the tests listed below, please complete Part II.)

Section A. Public Support

Calendar year (or fiscal year beginning in)	(a) 2012	(b) 2013	(c) 2014	(d) 2015	(e) 2016	(f) Total
1 Gifts, grants, contributions, and membership fees received (Do not include any "unusual grants.")						0
2 Gross receipts from admissions, merchandise sold or services performed, or facilities furnished in any activity that is related to the organization's tax-exempt purpose						0
3 Gross receipts from activities that are not an unrelated trade or business under section 513						0
4 Tax revenues levied for the organization's benefit and either paid to or expended on its behalf						0
5 The value of services or facilities furnished by a governmental unit to the organization without charge						0
6 Total. Add lines 1 through 5.	0	0	0	0	0	0
7a Amounts included on lines 1, 2, and 3 received from disqualified persons						0
b Amounts included on lines 2 and 3 received from other than disqualified persons that exceed the greater of \$5,000 or 1% of the amount on line 13 for the year						0
c Add lines 7a and 7b	0	0	0	0	0	0
8 Public support (Subtract line 7c from line 6)						0

Section B. Total Support

Calendar year (or fiscal year beginning in)	(a) 2012	(b) 2013	(c) 2014	(d) 2015	(e) 2016	(f) Total
9 Amounts from line 6	0	0	0	0	0	0
10a Gross income from interest, dividends, payments received on securities loans, rents, royalties and income from similar sources						0
b Unrelated business taxable income (less section 511 taxes) from businesses acquired after June 30, 1975						0
c Add lines 10a and 10b	0	0	0	0	0	0
11 Net income from unrelated business activities not included in line 10b, whether or not the business is regularly carried on						0
12 Other income. Do not include gain or loss from the sale of capital assets (Explain in Part VI)						0
13 Total support. (Add lines 9, 10c, 11, and 12.)	0	0	0	0	0	0

14 First five years. If the Form 990 is for the organization's first, second, third, fourth, or fifth tax year as a section 501(c)(3) organization, check this box and stop here

Section C. Computation of Public Support Percentage

15 Public support percentage for 2016 (line 8, column (f) divided by line 13, column (f))	15	0.00%
16 Public support percentage from 2015 Schedule A, Part III, line 15	16	0.00%

Section D. Computation of Investment Income Percentage

17 Investment income percentage for 2016 (line 10c, column (f) divided by line 13, column (f))	17	0.00%
18 Investment income percentage from 2015 Schedule A, Part III, line 17	18	0.00%

19a 33 1/3% support tests—2016. If the organization did not check the box on line 14, and line 15 is more than 33 1/3%, and line 17 is not more than 33 1/3%, check this box and stop here. The organization qualifies as a publicly supported organization

b 33 1/3% support tests—2015. If the organization did not check a box on line 14 or line 19a, and line 16 is more than 33 1/3%, and line 18 is not more than 33 1/3%, check this box and stop here. The organization qualifies as a publicly supported organization

20 Private foundation. If the organization did not check a box on line 14, 19a, or 19b, check this box and see instructions

Part IV Supporting Organizations

(Complete only if you checked a box in line 12 on Part I. If you checked 12a of Part I, complete Sections A and B. If you checked 12b of Part I, complete Sections A and C. If you checked 12c of Part I, complete Sections A, D, and E. If you checked 12d of Part I, complete Sections A and D, and complete Part V.)

Section A. All Supporting Organizations

		Yes	No
1	Are all of the organization's supported organizations listed by name in the organization's governing documents? If "No," describe in Part VI how the supported organizations are designated. If designated by class or purpose, describe the designation. If historic and continuing relationship, explain.		
2	Did the organization have any supported organization that does not have an IRS determination of status under section 509(a)(1) or (2)? If "Yes," explain in Part VI how the organization determined that the supported organization was described in section 509(a)(1) or (2).		
3a	Did the organization have a supported organization described in section 501(c)(4), (5), or (6)? If "Yes," answer (b) and (c) below.		
3b	Did the organization confirm that each supported organization qualified under section 501(c)(4), (5), or (6) and satisfied the public support tests under section 509(a)(2)? If "Yes," describe in Part VI when and how the organization made the determination.		
3c	Did the organization ensure that all support to such organizations was used exclusively for section 170(c)(2)(B) purposes? If "Yes," explain in Part VI what controls the organization put in place to ensure such use.		
4a	Was any supported organization not organized in the United States ("foreign supported organization")? If "Yes," and if you checked 12a or 12b in Part I, answer (b) and (c) below.		
4b	Did the organization have ultimate control and discretion in deciding whether to make grants to the foreign supported organization? If "Yes," describe in Part VI how the organization had such control and discretion despite being controlled or supervised by or in connection with its supported organizations.		
4c	Did the organization support any foreign supported organization that does not have an IRS determination under sections 501(c)(3) and 509(a)(1) or (2)? If "Yes," explain in Part VI what controls the organization used to ensure that all support to the foreign supported organization was used exclusively for section 170(c)(2)(B) purposes.		
5a	Did the organization add, substitute, or remove any supported organizations during the tax year? If "Yes," answer (b) and (c) below (if applicable). Also, provide detail in Part VI , including (i) the names and EIN numbers of the supported organizations added, substituted, or removed, (ii) the reasons for each such action, (iii) the authority under the organization's organizing document authorizing such action, and (iv) how the action was accomplished (such as by amendment to the organizing document).		
5b	Type I or Type II only. Was any added or substituted supported organization part of a class already designated in the organization's organizing document?		
5c	Substitutions only. Was the substitution the result of an event beyond the organization's control?		
6	Did the organization provide support (whether in the form of grants or the provision of services or facilities) to anyone other than (i) its supported organizations, (ii) individuals that are part of the charitable class benefited by one or more of its supported organizations, or (iii) other supporting organizations that also support or benefit one or more of the filing organization's supported organizations? If "Yes," provide detail in Part VI .		
7	Did the organization provide a grant, loan, compensation, or other similar payment to a substantial contributor (defined in section 4958(c)(3)(C)), a family member of a substantial contributor, or a 35% controlled entity with regard to a substantial contributor? If "Yes," complete Part I of Schedule L (Form 990 or 990-EZ).		
8	Did the organization make a loan to a disqualified person (as defined in section 4958) not described in line 7? If "Yes," complete Part I of Schedule L (Form 990 or 990-EZ).		
9a	Was the organization controlled directly or indirectly at any time during the tax year by one or more disqualified persons as defined in section 4946 (other than foundation managers and organizations described in section 509(a)(1) or (2))? If "Yes," provide detail in Part VI .		
9b	Did one or more disqualified persons (as defined in line 9a) hold a controlling interest in any entity in which the supporting organization had an interest? If "Yes," provide detail in Part VI .		
9c	Did a disqualified person (as defined in line 9a) have an ownership interest in, or derive any personal benefit from, assets in which the supporting organization also had an interest? If "Yes," provide detail in Part VI .		
10a	Was the organization subject to the excess business holdings rules of section 4943 because of section 4943(f) (regarding certain Type II supporting organizations, and all Type III non-functionally integrated supporting organizations)? If "Yes," answer 10b below.		
10b	Did the organization have any excess business holdings in the tax year? (Use Schedule C, Form 4720, to determine whether the organization had excess business holdings.)		

Part IV Supporting Organizations *(continued)*

		Yes	No
11	Has the organization accepted a gift or contribution from any of the following persons?		
a	A person who directly or indirectly controls, either alone or together with persons described in (b) and (c) below, the governing body of a supported organization?	11a	
b	A family member of a person described in (a) above?	11b	
c	A 35% controlled entity of a person described in (a) or (b) above? <i>If "Yes" to a, b, or c, provide detail in Part VI.</i>	11c	

Section B. Type I Supporting Organizations

		Yes	No
1	Did the directors, trustees, or membership of one or more supported organizations have the power to regularly appoint or elect at least a majority of the organization's directors or trustees at all times during the tax year? <i>If "No," describe in Part VI how the supported organization(s) effectively operated, supervised, or controlled the organization's activities. If the organization had more than one supported organization, describe how the powers to appoint and/or remove directors or trustees were allocated among the supported organizations and what conditions or restrictions, if any, applied to such powers during the tax year.</i>	1	
2	Did the organization operate for the benefit of any supported organization other than the supported organization(s) that operated, supervised, or controlled the supporting organization? <i>If "Yes," explain in Part VI how providing such benefit carried out the purposes of the supported organization(s) that operated, supervised, or controlled the supporting organization.</i>	2	

Section C. Type II Supporting Organizations

		Yes	No
1	Were a majority of the organization's directors or trustees during the tax year also a majority of the directors or trustees of each of the organization's supported organization(s)? <i>If "No," describe in Part VI how control or management of the supporting organization was vested in the same persons that controlled or managed the supported organization(s).</i>	1	

Section D. All Type III Supporting Organizations

		Yes	No
1	Did the organization provide to each of its supported organizations, by the last day of the fifth month of the organization's tax year, (i) a written notice describing the type and amount of support provided during the prior tax year, (ii) a copy of the Form 990 that was most recently filed as of the date of notification, and (iii) copies of the organization's governing documents in effect on the date of notification, to the extent not previously provided?	1	
2	Were any of the organization's officers, directors, or trustees either (i) appointed or elected by the supported organization(s) or (ii) serving on the governing body of a supported organization? <i>If "No," explain in Part VI how the organization maintained a close and continuous working relationship with the supported organization(s).</i>	2	
3	By reason of the relationship described in (2), did the organization's supported organizations have a significant voice in the organization's investment policies and in directing the use of the organization's income or assets at all times during the tax year? <i>If "Yes," describe in Part VI the role the organization's supported organizations played in this regard.</i>	3	

Section E. Type III Functionally Integrated Supporting Organizations

1	Check the box next to the method that the organization used to satisfy the Integral Part Test during the year (<i>see instructions</i>)		
a	☐ The organization satisfied the Activities Test. Complete line 2 below.		
b	☐ The organization is the parent of each of its supported organizations. Complete line 3 below.		
c	☐ The organization supported a governmental entity. Describe in Part VI how you supported a government entity (<i>see instructions</i>).		
2	Activities Test. Answer (a) and (b) below.		
a	Did substantially all of the organization's activities during the tax year directly further the exempt purposes of the supported organization(s) to which the organization was responsive? <i>If "Yes," then in Part VI identify those supported organizations and explain how these activities directly furthered their exempt purposes, how the organization was responsive to those supported organizations, and how the organization determined that these activities constituted substantially all of its activities.</i>	2a	
b	Did the activities described in (a) constitute activities that, but for the organization's involvement, one or more of the organization's supported organization(s) would have been engaged in? <i>If "Yes," explain in Part VI the reasons for the organization's position that its supported organization(s) would have engaged in these activities but for the organization's involvement.</i>	2b	
3	Parent of Supported Organizations. Answer (a) and (b) below.		
a	Did the organization have the power to regularly appoint or elect a majority of the officers, directors, or trustees of each of the supported organizations? <i>Provide details in Part VI.</i>	3a	
b	Did the organization exercise a substantial degree of direction over the policies, programs, and activities of each of its supported organizations? <i>If "Yes," describe in Part VI the role played by the organization in this regard.</i>	3b	

Part V Type III Non-Functionally Integrated 509(a)(3) Supporting Organizations

- 1 Check here if the organization satisfied the Integral Part Test as a qualifying trust on Nov. 20, 1970 (explain in Part VI) **See instructions.** All other Type III non-functionally integrated supporting organizations must complete Sections A through E

Section A - Adjusted Net Income		(A) Prior Year	(B) Current Year (optional)
1	Net short-term capital gain	1	
2	Recoveries of prior-year distributions	2	
3	Other gross income (see instructions)	3	
4	Add lines 1 through 3	4	0
5	Depreciation and depletion	5	
6	Portion of operating expenses paid or incurred for production or collection of gross income or for management, conservation, or maintenance of property held for production of income (see instructions)	6	
7	Other expenses (see instructions)	7	
8	Adjusted Net Income (subtract lines 5, 6, and 7 from line 4)	8	0
Section B - Minimum Asset Amount		(A) Prior Year	(B) Current Year (optional)
1	Aggregate fair market value of all non-exempt-use assets (see instructions for short tax year or assets held for part of year)		
a	Average monthly value of securities	1a	
b	Average monthly cash balances	1b	
c	Fair market value of other non-exempt-use assets	1c	
d	Total (add lines 1a, 1b, and 1c)	1d	0
e	Discount claimed for blockage or other factors (explain in detail in Part VI)		
2	Acquisition indebtedness applicable to non-exempt-use assets	2	
3	Subtract line 2 from line 1d	3	0
4	Cash deemed held for exempt use Enter 1-1/2% of line 3 (for greater amount, see instructions)	4	0
5	Net value of non-exempt-use assets (subtract line 4 from line 3)	5	0
6	Multiply line 5 by .035	6	0
7	Recoveries of prior-year distributions	7	0
8	Minimum Asset Amount (add line 7 to line 6)	8	0
Section C - Distributable Amount			Current Year
1	Adjusted net income for prior year (from Section A, line 8, Column A)	1	0
2	Enter 85% of line 1	2	0
3	Minimum asset amount for prior year (from Section B, line 8, Column A)	3	0
4	Enter greater of line 2 or line 3	4	0
5	Income tax imposed in prior year	5	
6	Distributable Amount. Subtract line 5 from line 4, unless subject to emergency temporary reduction (see instructions)	6	0
7	☐ Check here if the current year is the organization's first as a non-functionally integrated Type III supporting organization (see instructions)		

Part V Type III Non-Functionally Integrated 509(a)(3) Supporting Organizations (continued)

Section D - Distributions		Current Year		
1	Amounts paid to supported organizations to accomplish exempt purposes			
2	Amounts paid to perform activity that directly furthers exempt purposes of supported organizations, in excess of income from activity			
3	Administrative expenses paid to accomplish exempt purposes of supported organizations			
4	Amounts paid to acquire exempt-use assets			
5	Qualified set-aside amounts (prior IRS approval required)			
6	Other distributions (describe in Part VI) See instructions			
7	Total annual distributions. Add lines 1 through 6			0
8	Distributions to attentive supported organizations to which the organization is responsive (provide details in Part VI) See instructions			
9	Distributable amount for 2016 from Section C, line 6			0
10	Line 8 amount divided by Line 9 amount			0.000
Section E - Distribution Allocations (see instructions)		(i) Excess Distributions	(ii) Underdistributions Pre-2016	(iii) Distributable Amount for 2016
1	Distributable amount for 2016 from Section C, line 6			0
2	Underdistributions, if any, for years prior to 2016 (reasonable cause required—explain in Part VI) See instructions			
3	Excess distributions carryover, if any, to 2016			
a				
b				
c	From 2013	0		
d	From 2014	0		
e	From 2015	0		
f	Total of lines 3a through e	0		
g	Applied to underdistributions of prior years		0	
h	Applied to 2016 distributable amount			0
i	Carryover from 2011 not applied (see instructions)			
j	Remainder Subtract lines 3g, 3h, and 3i from 3f	0		
4	Distributions for 2016 from Section D, line 7 \$ 0			
a	Applied to underdistributions of prior years		0	
b	Applied to 2016 distributable amount			0
c	Remainder Subtract lines 4a and 4b from 4	0		
5	Remaining underdistributions for years prior to 2016, if any Subtract lines 3g and 4a from line 2 For result greater than zero, explain in Part VI See instructions		0	
6	Remaining underdistributions for 2016 Subtract lines 3h and 4b from line 1 For result greater than zero, explain in Part VI See instructions			0
7	Excess distributions carryover to 2017. Add lines 3j and 4c	0		
8	Breakdown of line 7			
a				
b	Excess from 2013	0		
c	Excess from 2014	0		
d	Excess from 2015	0		
e	Excess from 2016	0		

**SCHEDULE D
(Form 990)**

Supplemental Financial Statements

▶ Complete if the organization answered "Yes" on Form 990, Part IV, line 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11a, 11b, 11c, 11d, 11e, 11f, 12a, or 12b.
▶ Attach to Form 990.

OMB No 1545-0047

2016

Open to Public Inspection

Department of the Treasury
Internal Revenue Service

▶ Information about Schedule D (Form 990) and its instructions is at www.irs.gov/form990.

Name of the organization FACES & VOICES OF RECOVERY	Employer identification number 51-0516206
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Part I Organizations Maintaining Donor Advised Funds or Other Similar Funds or Accounts.
Complete if the organization answered "Yes" on Form 990, Part IV, line 6

	(a) Donor advised funds	(b) Funds and other accounts
1 Total number at end of year		
2 Aggregate value of contributions to (during year)		
3 Aggregate value of grants from (during year)		
4 Aggregate value at end of year		
5 Did the organization inform all donors and donor advisors in writing that the assets held in donor advised funds are the organization's property, subject to the organization's exclusive legal control?		☐ Yes ☐ No
6 Did the organization inform all grantees, donors, and donor advisors in writing that grant funds can be used only for charitable purposes and not for the benefit of the donor or donor advisor, or for any other purpose conferring impermissible private benefit?		☐ Yes ☐ No

Part II Conservation Easements.
Complete if the organization answered "Yes" on Form 990, Part IV, line 7.

1 Purpose(s) of conservation easements held by the organization (check all that apply)	
☐ Preservation of land for public use (e.g., recreation or education)	☐ Preservation of a historically important land area
☐ Protection of natural habitat	☐ Preservation of a certified historic structure
☐ Preservation of open space	
2 Complete lines 2a through 2d if the organization held a qualified conservation contribution in the form of a conservation easement on the last day of the tax year	
a Total number of conservation easements	Held at the End of the Tax Year
b Total acreage restricted by conservation easements	2a
c Number of conservation easements on a certified historic structure included in (a)	2b
d Number of conservation easements included in (c) acquired after 8/17/06, and not on a historic structure listed in the National Register	2c
3 Number of conservation easements modified, transferred, released, extinguished, or terminated by the organization during the tax year ▶	2d
4 Number of states where property subject to conservation easement is located ▶	
5 Does the organization have a written policy regarding the periodic monitoring, inspection, handling of violations, and enforcement of the conservation easements it holds?	☐ Yes ☐ No
6 Staff and volunteer hours devoted to monitoring, inspecting, handling of violations, and enforcing conservation easements during the year ▶	
7 Amount of expenses incurred in monitoring, inspecting, handling of violations, and enforcing conservation easements during the year ▶ \$	
8 Does each conservation easement reported on line 2(d) above satisfy the requirements of section 170(h)(4)(B)(i) and section 170(h)(4)(B)(ii)?	☐ Yes ☐ No
9 In Part XIII, describe how the organization reports conservation easements in its revenue and expense statement, and balance sheet, and include, if applicable, the text of the footnote to the organization's financial statements that describes the organization's accounting for conservation easements	

Part III Organizations Maintaining Collections of Art, Historical Treasures, or Other Similar Assets.
Complete if the organization answered "Yes" on Form 990, Part IV, line 8

1a If the organization elected, as permitted under SFAS 116 (ASC 958), not to report in its revenue statement and balance sheet works of art, historical treasures, or other similar assets held for public exhibition, education, or research in furtherance of public service, provide, in Part XIII, the text of the footnote to its financial statements that describes these items	
b If the organization elected, as permitted under SFAS 116 (ASC 958), to report in its revenue statement and balance sheet works of art, historical treasures, or other similar assets held for public exhibition, education, or research in furtherance of public service, provide the following amounts relating to these items:	
(i) Revenue included on Form 990, Part VIII, line 1	▶ \$ _____
(ii) Assets included in Form 990, Part X	▶ \$ _____
2 If the organization received or held works of art, historical treasures, or other similar assets for financial gain, provide the following amounts required to be reported under SFAS 116 (ASC 958) relating to these items	
a Revenue included on Form 990, Part VIII, line 1	▶ \$ _____
b Assets included in Form 990, Part X	▶ \$ _____

Part III Organizations Maintaining Collections of Art, Historical Treasures, or Other Similar Assets (continued)

- 3 Using the organization's acquisition, accession, and other records, check any of the following that are a significant use of its collection items (check all that apply)
- a Public exhibition
 - b Scholarly research
 - c Preservation for future generations
 - d Loan or exchange programs
 - e Other
- 4 Provide a description of the organization's collections and explain how they further the organization's exempt purpose in Part XIII
- 5 During the year, did the organization solicit or receive donations of art, historical treasures, or other similar assets to be sold to raise funds rather than to be maintained as part of the organization's collection? Yes No

Part IV Escrow and Custodial Arrangements.

Complete if the organization answered "Yes" on Form 990, Part IV, line 9, or reported an amount on Form 990, Part X, line 21.

- 1a Is the organization an agent, trustee, custodian or other intermediary for contributions or other assets not included on Form 990, Part X? Yes No
- b If "Yes," explain the arrangement in Part XIII and complete the following table
- | | Amount |
|---------------------------------|--------|
| c Beginning balance | 0 |
| d Additions during the year | |
| e Distributions during the year | |
| f Ending balance | 0 |
- 2a Did the organization include an amount on Form 990, Part X, line 21, for escrow or custodial account liability? Yes No
- b If "Yes," explain the arrangement in Part XIII. Check here if the explanation has been provided on Part XIII

Part V Endowment Funds.

Complete if the organization answered "Yes" on Form 990, Part IV, line 10

	(a) Current year	(b) Prior year	(c) Two years back	(d) Three years back	(e) Four years back
1a Beginning of year balance	0	0	0	0	0
b Contributions					
c Net investment earnings, gains, and losses					
d Grants or scholarships					
e Other expenditures for facilities and programs					
f Administrative expenses					
g End of year balance	0	0	0	0	0

- 2 Provide the estimated percentage of the current year end balance (line 1g, column (a)) held as
- a Board designated or quasi-endowment ▶ _____ %
 - b Permanent endowment ▶ _____ %
 - c Temporarily restricted endowment ▶ _____ %
- The percentages on lines 2a, 2b, and 2c should equal 100%
- 3a Are there endowment funds not in the possession of the organization that are held and administered for the organization by:
- | | Yes | No |
|--|-----|----|
| (i) unrelated organizations | | |
| (ii) related organizations | | |
| b If "Yes" on line 3a(ii), are the related organizations listed as required on Schedule R? | | |
- 4 Describe in Part XIII the intended uses of the organization's endowment funds

Part VI Land, Buildings, and Equipment.

Complete if the organization answered "Yes" on Form 990, Part IV, line 11a. See Form 990, Part X, line 10.

Description of property	(a) Cost or other basis (investment)	(b) Cost or other basis (other)	(c) Accumulated depreciation	(d) Book value
1a Land	0	0	0	0
b Buildings	0	0	0	0
c Leasehold improvements	0	0	0	0
d Equipment	0	6,021	968	5,053
e Other	0	74,246	72,233	2,013

Total. Add lines 1a through 1e (Column (d) must equal Form 990, Part X, column (B), line 10c) ▶ 7,066

Part VII Investments—Other Securities.

Complete if the organization answered "Yes" on Form 990, Part IV, line 11b. See Form 990, Part X, line 12

(a) Description of security or category (including name of security)	(b) Book value	(c) Method of valuation Cost or end-of-year market value
(1) Financial derivatives	0	
(2) Closely-held equity interests	0	
(3) Other		
(A) -----		
(B) -----		
(C) -----		
(D) -----		
(E) -----		
(F) -----		
(G) -----		
(H) -----		
Total. (Column (b) must equal Form 990, Part X, col (B) line 12)	0	

Part VIII Investments—Program Related.

Complete if the organization answered "Yes" on Form 990, Part IV, line 11c. See Form 990, Part X, line 13

(a) Description of investment	(b) Book value	(c) Method of valuation Cost or end-of-year market value
(1)		
(2)		
(3)		
(4)		
(5)		
(6)		
(7)		
(8)		
(9)		
Total. (Column (b) must equal Form 990, Part X, col (B) line 13)	0	

Part IX Other Assets.

Complete if the organization answered "Yes" on Form 990, Part IV, line 11d. See Form 990, Part X, line 15

(a) Description	(b) Book value
(1) DEPOSITS	2,999
(2) EMPLOYEE ADVANCES	637
(3)	
(4)	
(5)	
(6)	
(7)	
(8)	
(9)	
Total. (Column (b) must equal Form 990, Part X, col (B) line 15)	3,636

Part X Other Liabilities.

Complete if the organization answered "Yes" on Form 990, Part IV, line 11e or 11f. See Form 990, Part X, line 25.

1. (a) Description of liability	(b) Book value
(1) Federal income taxes	0
(2) ACCRUED EXPENSES	12,597
(3) PAYROLL TAX WITHHOLDING	1,848
(4) DUE TO OTHERS	22,275
(5)	
(6)	
(7)	
(8)	
(9)	
Total. (Column (b) must equal Form 990, Part X, col (B) line 25)	36,720

2. Liability for uncertain tax positions In Part XIII, provide the text of the footnote to the organization's financial statements that reports the organization's liability for uncertain tax positions under FIN 48 (ASC 740). Check here if the text of the footnote has been provided in Part XIII

Part XIII Supplemental Information *(continued)*

Area with horizontal dashed lines for supplemental information.

Part II Fundraising Events. Complete if the organization answered "Yes" on Form 990, Part IV, line 18, or reported more than \$15,000 of fundraising event contributions and gross income on Form 990-EZ, lines 1 and 6b. List events with gross receipts greater than \$5,000

		(a) Event #1	(b) Event #2	(c) Other events	(d) Total events
		Merica Honors Recov (event type)	(event type)	NONE (total number)	(add col (a) through col (c))
Revenue	1	Gross receipts	127,300	0	127,300
	2	Less Contributions	127,300	0	127,300
	3	Gross income (line 1 minus line 2)	0	0	0
Direct Expenses	4	Cash prizes		0	0
	5	Noncash prizes		0	0
	6	Rent/facility costs		0	0
	7	Food and beverages		0	0
	8	Entertainment		0	0
	9	Other direct expenses		0	0
	10	Direct expense summary Add lines 4 through 9 in column (d)			▶
11	Net income summary Subtract line 10 from line 3, column (d)			▶	0

Part III Gaming. Complete if the organization answered "Yes" on Form 990, Part IV, line 19, or reported more than \$15,000 on Form 990-EZ, line 6a

		(a) Bingo	(b) Pull tabs/instant bingo/progressive bingo	(c) Other gaming	(d) Total gaming (add col (a) through col (c))
Revenue	1	Gross revenue			0
Direct Expenses	2	Cash prizes			0
	3	Noncash prizes			0
	4	Rent/facility costs			0
	5	Other direct expenses			0
6	Volunteer labor	☐ Yes _____ % ☐ No	☐ Yes _____ % ☐ No	☐ Yes _____ % ☐ No	
7	Direct expense summary Add lines 2 through 5 in column (d)			▶	(0)
8	Net gaming income summary Subtract line 7 from line 1, column (d)			▶	0

- 9 Enter the state(s) in which the organization conducts gaming activities _____
- a Is the organization licensed to conduct gaming activities in each of these states? Yes No
- b If "No," explain _____
- 10a Were any of the organization's gaming licenses revoked, suspended, or terminated during the tax year? Yes No
- b If "Yes," explain _____

SCHEDULE O
(Form 990 or 990-EZ)

Supplemental Information to Form 990 or 990-EZ

Complete to provide information for responses to specific questions on
Form 990 or 990-EZ or to provide any additional information.

▶ Attach to Form 990 or 990-EZ.

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2016

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Internal Revenue Service

▶ Information about Schedule O (Form 990 or 990-EZ) and its instructions is at www.irs.gov/form990.

Name of the organization

Employer identification number

FACES & VOICES OF RECOVERY

51-0516206

Form 990, Part VI, Section B, Line 11A A COPY OF FORM 990 IS DISTRIBUTED TO ALL MEMBERS OF

THE BOARD VIA EMAIL BEFORE FILING

Form 990, Part VI, Section C, Line 19 THE ORGANIZATIONS GOVERNING DOCUMENTS, CONFLICT OF

INTEREST POLICY AND FINANCIAL STATEMENTS ARE MADE AVAILABLE TO THE PUBLIC UPON REQUEST.

Name of the organization

Employer identification number

FACES & VOICES OF RECOVERY

51-0516206

Area with horizontal dashed lines for supplemental information.